

AN ENERGY APPROACH FOR THE PREDICTION OF EFFECTIVE STIFFNESS OF 2-D BRAIDED COMPOSITES

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Summary: A microstructure model of 2-D braided composite is developed. Fiber volume fractions are evaluated by this model and compared with experimental results. Upper limit of fiber volume fraction is also obtained. Effective stiffness of 2-D braided composite is obtained in a closed form by the analysis of elastic deformation energy in repeat-unit-cell (RUC) of braided composites. Effective stiffness consists of contributions of axial yarn, braiding yarn, and matrix material. Each of them takes a different contribution in the effective stiffness. The fractions of contribution of axial yarn, braiding yarn, and matrix material are $\chi V_f/k$, $(1-\chi)V_f/k$, and $(1-V_f/k)$ respectively, where V_f is the fiber volume fraction, χ is the axial yarn content in a braided composite, and k is the filament packing fraction. The results of effective stiffness predicted are very good as compared with experimental results. The independent parameters in design and analysis of 2-D braided composites are successfully separated from all other parameters. This greatly reduces the difficulties of design and analysis of 2-D braided composites.

Keyword: braided composite, effective stiffness, parameter analysis, fiber volume fraction, elastic deformation energy

INTRODUCTION

Braiding is a simple and versatile textile process in which two or more systems of yarn are intertwined in bias direction to form an integrated structure called braided fabric preform. Braided composite is manufactured by applying resin to the braided fabric preform. As compared to traditional laminated composites, braided composites have low cost, improved damage resistance, better through-the-thickness and inter-laminar strength. Braiding processes have the ability to fabricate a wide range of complex shapes. Braiding process can form shapes either by over-braiding mandrels on conventional machine (2-D process) or by using new braiding processes to form solid shapes (3-D process). 2-D braided laminate of a certain desired thickness is formed by over-braiding layers of the desired architecture on top of each other. This leads to a two dimensional material as there are no interlayer yarns through the laminate thickness. 3-D braided fabrics have been produced on traditional horn-gear machines for ropes with circular, or square cross-sections. A number of new machines without the traditional horn gears have been developed to create complex shapes. The new braiding processes include: two-step[1], AYPEX[2], four-steps[3] and multi-step[4,5].

The purpose of this research is to study the structure and the effective stiffness of two dimensional braided composite. Effective stiffness of braided composite has been studied by several researchers [6-11]. There are mainly four different approaches for calculating the effective stiffness of 2-D braided composite: (1) Laminate approach This is the simplest approach which ignores the out of plane undulations of braided yarns and treats each set of yarns as unidirectional ply in a $(0/\pm\theta)$ symmetric laminate[6] (2) Diagonal brick approach This is based on the concept of a simplified unit cell representation of the composite-reinforcing microstructure. The brick shape unit cell consists of four parallel bar elements along four edges of the brick and four diagonal bar elements [7]. The stiffness of the bar elements (EA/L) are chosen such that they reflect the amount of fiber reinforcement within the unit cell. (3) Stress averaging approach [8] This is based on an iso-strain assumption within RUC. Each yarn segment is discretized into yarn slices first, then the average stresses in the RUC were found by first transforming yarn slice stress to the global RUC coordinate and then computing the volume average of the stress in all the yarn slices. This approach is adopted by Naik, R., A.[9] in his research work. (4) Finite element approach This approach were developed by several authors [10,11]. This approach analyzes a detailed unit cell of the composite material.

In this paper an energy approach based on iso-strain assumption is developed to analyze the effective stiffness of 2-D braided composites. The energy approach proposed here has several advantages as compared with other approaches mentioned above: (1) The equation of effective stiffness is in closed form which helps to convey physical relations. Each contribution of axial yarn, braiding yarn, and matrix material can be separated clearly. (2) The independent parameters in the design and analysis of 2-D braided composites can be separated from all other parameters easily. (3) The predicted results of effective stiffness by this approach are good as compared with experimental results. (4)The calculating time is much shorter than that of finite element approach.

GEOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF 2-D BRAIDED COMPOSITE

Yarn Cross Section

The cross sectional area of a yarn is assumed to have the shape as shown in Fig. 1. The upper and lower boundaries of yarn are arcs with the same radius. Let the thickness to width ratio be

$$x = \frac{t}{w} \quad (1)$$

where t , w are the thickness and width of yarn respectively. Assume that both axial yarn and braiding yarn have the same thickness to width ratio ξ , the cross sectional areas are as follows:

$$A_a = l t_a^2 \quad (2)$$

$$A_b = l t_b^2 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1: The cross sectional area of yarn

where A_a , A_b are the cross sectional areas of axial and braiding yarn respectively. Subscript a, b denote axial yarn and braiding yarn respectively. λ is given by [14]

$$\lambda = \left[\frac{(1+x^2)^2}{8x^4} \arcsin\left(\frac{2x}{1+x^2}\right) - \frac{(1-x^2)}{4x^3} \right] \quad (4)$$

Assume the cross sectional area of a yarn is proportional to its filament count number and the filament cross section has circular shape with a constant diameter d_f , then

$$kA_a = m_a \times \left(\frac{\rho}{4} d_f^2\right) \quad (5)$$

$$kA_b = m_b \times \left(\frac{\rho}{4} d_f^2\right) \quad (6)$$

where m_a , m_b are the filament count numbers of axial yarn and braiding yarn respectively, d_f is the diameter of filament, k is the filament packing fraction which has been studied by a number of researchers primarily for textile applications [12]. Substitute Eqn 2, 3 to Eqn 5, 6 respectively, then

$$t_a = \sqrt{\frac{\rho m_a}{4kl}} \times d_f \quad (7)$$

$$t_b = \sqrt{\frac{\rho m_b}{4kl}} \times d_f \quad (8)$$

If the values of m_a , m_b , d_f , ξ are known, then A_a , A_b , W_a , W_b , t_a , t_b can be obtained.

Fiber Volume Fraction

Fiber volume fraction is the ratio of volume of total filaments to the volume of braided composite which consists of these filaments. The fiber volume fraction can be obtained from A-A section of Fig. 2,

$$V_f = \frac{k(NA_b' + \frac{N}{2} A_a)}{\rho D(2t_b + t_a)} \quad (9)$$

where N is the number of braiding yarn carriers. The number of axial yarn carriers is $N/2$. D is the diameter of mandrel of braided preform.

$$A_b' = \frac{A_b}{\cos\theta} \quad (10)$$

where θ is the braiding angle. Substitute Eqn 2, 3, 7, 8,10 into Eqn 9, then

$$V_f = \frac{kN(1 + \frac{m_a}{2m_b} \cos\theta) t_b}{\rho D \cos\theta (2 + \sqrt{\frac{m_a}{m_b}})} \quad (11)$$

Upper Limit of Fiber Volume Fraction

Fiber volume fraction is assumed to attain to its maximum value when yarn jamming happens. The upper limit of fiber volume fraction can be obtained from Fig. 2 as follows,

$$NA'_b + \frac{NA_a}{2} \leq \rho D(2t_b + t_a)lx \quad (12)$$

Substituting Eqn 12 into Eqn 9, then the upper limit of fiber volume fraction V_f is

$$V_f \leq kxl \quad (13)$$

Fig. 2: Triaxial 2-D braided preform

Jamming Angle θ_J

The jamming angle can be derived from Fig. 2. If no overlap of yarn happens, then

$$W'_b \leq L \quad (14)$$

where L is the yarn space defined as the distance between two adjacent axial yarns, so

$$L = \frac{\rho D}{N/2} \quad (15)$$

$$W'_b = \frac{W_b}{\cos q} \quad (16)$$

Substitute Eqn 16 to Eqn 14, then

$$q_J = \arccos\left(\frac{W_b}{L}\right) \quad (17)$$

Yarn Crimp Angle

The path of braiding yarn (shown in Fig. 3) is cut out from Fig. 2 in B-B section. It is assumed to be sinusoidal, then it can be described as,

$$z = \frac{t_a + t_b}{2} \sin\left(\frac{\rho x}{2L}\right) \quad (18)$$

where

$$L' = \frac{L}{2 \sin \varphi} \quad (19)$$

Substituting Eqn 19,15 into Eqn 18, yields

$$z = \frac{t_a + t_b}{2} \sin\left(\frac{N \sin \varphi}{2D} x\right) \quad (20)$$

So the crimp angle γ is defined as

$$\tan \gamma = \frac{dz}{dx} \Big|_{x=0} = \frac{(t_a + t_b)N}{4D} \sin \varphi \quad (21)$$

Fig. 3: Cross section along braiding yarn direction

EFFECTIVE STIFFNESS

An energy approach is used to deduce the effective stiffness of braided composite. The braided composites consist of impregnated axial yarns, braiding yarns and matrix material. The matrix material is isotropic. Straight impregnated yarn is transversely isotropic. The iso-strain assumption is adopted in this research. A RUC is cut from composite as shown in Fig. 4. The global RUC coordinate system xyz is also shown in Fig. 4. The elastic deformation energy of left and right half RUC are same, so only the left half RUC (shown in Fig. 5) is chosen for energy analysis. The elastic deformation energy stored in left half RUC is

$$E = E_b + E_a + E_m \quad (22)$$

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \{e\}^T [\bar{C}] \{e\} Ah \quad (23)$$

Where E_b , E_a , E_m are the elastic deformation energy stored in the braiding yarn segments, axial yarn segments, and matrix material respectively. $[\bar{C}]$ is a 6×6 effective stiffness matrix. h is the height of RUC. $\{\varepsilon\} = \{\varepsilon_{xx}, \varepsilon_{yy}, \varepsilon_{zz}, \gamma_{yz}, \gamma_{zx}, \gamma_{xy}\}^T$ is global engineering strain vector. A is the top area of the left half RUC.

$$A = (t_a + 2t_b) L \quad (24)$$

Fig. 4: Repeat unit cell (RUC)

Fig. 5: Left half RUC (axial yarn and -q braiding yarn are not shown)

Fig. 6: The principal coordinate system of yarn and global RUC coordinate system

There is only one axial yarn segment in the left half RUC, so the elastic deformation energy stored in this axial yarn segment is

$$E_a = \frac{1}{2} \{e\}^T [C_y] \{e\} A_a h \quad (25)$$

where $[C_y]$ is a 6×6 stiffness matrix of impregnated straight yarn. The relation between yarn principal coordinate system 123 and global RUC coordinate system xyz is shown in Fig. 6. There are two braiding yarn segments with $\pm\theta$ in the left half RUC, so the elastic deformation energy of the braiding yarn segments is

$$E_b = \frac{1}{2} \{e\}^T \left([C_b]_{+q} + [C_b]_{-q} \right) \{e\} \frac{A_b h}{\cos\theta} \quad (26)$$

where

$$[C_b] = \frac{1}{S} \int_{-L'}^{L'} [B]^T [C_y] [B] \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{dz}{dx}\right)^2} dx \quad (27)$$

$$[B] = [A][T][A]^{-1} \quad (28)$$

$$[A] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} l_{11}^2 & l_{12}^2 & l_{13}^2 & 2l_{12}l_{13} & 2l_{13}l_{11} & 2l_{11}l_{12} \\ l_{21}^2 & l_{22}^2 & l_{23}^2 & 2l_{22}l_{23} & 2l_{23}l_{21} & 2l_{21}l_{22} \\ l_{31}^2 & l_{32}^2 & l_{33}^2 & 2l_{32}l_{33} & 2l_{33}l_{31} & 2l_{31}l_{32} \\ l_{21}l_{31} & l_{22}l_{32} & l_{23}l_{33} & (l_{22}l_{33} + l_{32}l_{23}) & (l_{23}l_{31} + l_{33}l_{21}) & (l_{21}l_{32} + l_{31}l_{22}) \\ l_{31}l_{11} & l_{32}l_{12} & l_{33}l_{13} & (l_{32}l_{13} + l_{12}l_{33}) & (l_{33}l_{11} + l_{13}l_{31}) & (l_{31}l_{12} + l_{11}l_{32}) \\ l_{11}l_{21} & l_{12}l_{22} & l_{13}l_{23} & (l_{12}l_{23} + l_{22}l_{13}) & (l_{13}l_{21} + l_{23}l_{11}) & (l_{11}l_{22} + l_{21}l_{12}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} l_{11} & l_{12} & l_{13} \\ l_{21} & l_{22} & l_{23} \\ l_{31} & l_{32} & l_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos q \cos \chi & \cos q \sin \chi & \sin q \\ -\sin \chi & \cos \chi & 0 \\ -\sin q \cos \chi & -\sin q \sin \chi & \cos q \end{bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

S is the length of braiding yarn segment .

The elastic deformation energy stored in matrix material of the left half RUC is

$$E_m = \frac{1}{2} \{e\}^T [C_m] \{e\} A_m h \quad (32)$$

where $[C_m]$ is a 6×6 stiffness matrix of matrix material. $A_m = A - (A_a + 2A_b)$.

Substituting Eqn 23, 25, 26, 32 into Eqn (22), gives the effective stiffness of braided composites,

$$[\bar{C}] = \left(\frac{[C_b]_{+\chi} + [C_b]_{-\chi}}{2 \cos q} \right) \frac{(1-c)V_f}{k} + [C_y] c \frac{V_f}{k} + [C_m] \left(1 - \frac{V_f}{k}\right) \quad (33)$$

where χ is axial yarn content of braid preform

$$c = \frac{\frac{m_a}{2m_b}}{\frac{1}{\cos q} + \frac{m_a}{2m_b}} \times 100\% \quad (34)$$

The above equation reveals a physical relation. The effective stiffness consists of contributions of axial yarn, braiding yarn and matrix material. The fractions of contribution of axial yarn, braiding yarn and matrix material are $\chi V_f/k$, $(1-\chi)V_f/k$ and $(1-V_f/k)$ respectively.

ANALYTICAL RESULTS

Fiber Volume Fraction and Its Upper Limit

Four material types are evaluated in this paper. The material type, yarn space, number of layers, thickness of laminates are obtained from [13]. The 2-D triaxially braided composites used here were made from AS4 graphite fiber impregnated with 1895 epoxy resin. The filament diameter of AS4 graphite fiber is 0.007mm. The experimental and the predicted results of fiber volume fraction are listed in Table 1. The maximum relative error between the values of experiment and theory is about 6%, which happens both in the case of $[0_{30k}/\pm 70_{6k}]$ 46% Axial, and the case $[0_{6k}/\pm 45_{15k}]$ 12% Axial.

Table 1: The fiber volume fraction from experiment [13] and proposed theory

Material type	Yarn space L (mm)	Number of layers N_L	Thickness of laminates H (mm)	Fiber volume fraction V_f [13]	Fiber volume fraction V_f (Predicted)
$[0_{30K}/\pm 70_{6K}]$ 46% Axial	6.05	8	5.66	55.3	58.5
$[0_{75k}/\pm 70_{15K}]$ 46% Axial	11.04	6	5.61	59.4	58.9
$[0_{36k}/\pm 45_{15K}]$ 46% Axial	5.52	6	5.64	58.4	58.2
$[0_{6k}/\pm 45_{15K}]$ 12% Axial	5.52	10	5.66	56.4	58.8

From Eqn 13 the theoretical upper limits of fiber volume fraction are $V_f=58.9\%$ for $\xi = 1$ and $V_f = 50\%$ for $\xi = 0$ with $k=0.75$. It means that when $k=0.75$, the maximum fiber volume fraction will never be over 58.9%.

Effective Stiffness

The predicted values of fiber volume fraction V_f in Table 1 are used to calculate the effective stiffness of braided composite. The elastic constants of impregnated straight yarn and resin are listed in Table 2. Eqn 33 is used to predict the effective stiffness of the four material types listed in Table 1. The predicted values of effective stiffness are listed in Table 3. The maximum relative errors between the experimental [13] and predicted results of E_{xx} , E_{yy} , G_{xy} , ν_{xy} are 5.17%, 7.4%, 7.23%, 1.53% respectively.

Analysis of Independent Parameters

Filament packing fraction k and diameter d_f , yarn count number m_a , m_b , thickness to width ratio ξ , braiding angle θ , yarn space L , elastic constants of resin and impregnated straight yarn are independent parameters. They can be changed independently. All other parameters depend on them. A complete analysis of independent parameters is discussed in [14].

Distributions of dependent parameters such as yarn thickness and width, fiber volume fraction, effective stiffness can be obtained according to the variation of independent parameters.

The conclusions obtained from the analysis of independent parameters are as follows:

(1) Increase of braiding angle or decrease of yarn space will increase the fiber volume fraction until yarn jamming happens.

(2) Increase of braiding angle, count number of axial yarn, or decrease of yarn space will increase the crimp angle.

(3) Increase of fiber volume fraction does not always increase the effective E_{xx} and G_{xy} . If the increase of fiber volume fraction only comes from the increase of braiding angle, the more is the fiber volume fraction the less is the effective E_{xx} .

Table 2: Elastic constants of impregnated straight yarn and resin [13]

Material	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{23}
Yarn	144.80	11.73	5.52	0.23	0.3
Resin	3.45	3.45	1.28	0.35	0.35

Table 3: The predicted and experimental results of effective stiffness

Material type	Axial Modulus E_{xx} (GPa)		Transverse Modulus E_{yy} (GPa)		Shear Modulus G_{xy} (GPa)		Poisson's ratio ν_{xy}	
	Exp.[13]	Theory	Exp.[13]	Theory	Exp.[13]	Theory	Exp.[13]	Theory
[0 _{30k} /±70 _{6k}] 46% Axial	55.67	58.55	49.3	52.85	9.68	10.38	0.15	0.152
[0 _{75k} /±70 _{15k}]46% Axial	59.63	58.54	53.38	53.31	10.38	10.43	0.15	0.152
[0 _{36k} /±45 _{15k}]46% Axial	62.67	62.68	20.78	21.47	18.04	18.25	0.65	0.642
[0 _{6k} /±45 _{15k}]12% Axial	27.92	28.87	20.13	21.16	26.00	26.99	0.73	0.724

CONCLUSIONS

A microstructure model of 2-D braided composite is formulated in this study. Fiber volume fractions are evaluated by this model and are compared with experimental results. The upper limit of fiber volume fraction is also given by this study. Effective stiffness of 2-D braided composite is obtained in closed form by the analysis of elastic deformation energy in RUC of braided composites. The effective stiffness consists of contributions of axial yarn, braiding yarn, and matrix material. The fractions of contribution of axial yarn, braiding yarn, and matrix material are $\chi V_f/k$, $(1-\chi)V_f/k$, and $(1-V_f/k)$ respectively. The predicted values of effective stiffness are very good as compared with experimental results[13]. Independent parameters in design and analysis of 2-D braided composites are successfully separated from all other parameters.

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